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Measurement of Course outcome and program Outcome for Accreditation of Diploma Engineering Institute

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ABSTRACT

In Outcome-Based Education (OBE), the assessment of Course Outcomes (COs) and Program Outcomes (POs) is a critical aspect in ensuring and enhancing the quality of technical education. A Course Outcome is a specific statement that defines the knowledge, skills, and competencies a student is expected to acquire at the end of a course. On the other hand, Program Outcomes represent the broader knowledge, abilities, and attitudes that students should demonstrate upon completion of the entire program.

Since POs are achieved through the attainment of COs, the measurement of COs provides a direct means to evaluate POs. This paper presents a simple yet effective approach to measuring the attainment of COs and POs using both direct assessment methods (such as examinations, assignments, and laboratory work) and indirect assessment methods (such as surveys, feedback, and self-assessment).

The analysis of attainment levels serves as a feedback mechanism to improve the teaching–learning process, which forms a vital component of the OBE framework. By systematically monitoring and evaluating outcomes, institutions can identify gaps, implement corrective measures, and continuously enhance the overall effectiveness of technical education.

Introduction

The Outcome-Based Education (OBE) system has emerged as one of the most significant approaches in engineering and technical education worldwide. In India, the adoption of OBE has been formalised through the National Board of Accreditation (NBA), which emphasises student-centric learning and measurable outcomes.

OBE can be defined as “*an outcome is a visible and observable demonstration of knowledge, competence, and orientation at the end of the learning experience*” (Spady, 1994) [1]. This definition highlights that learning outcomes should not remain abstract goals but must be demonstrated in the form of student performance, skills, and professional attributes.

For effective implementation of OBE in technical education, it is necessary to:

1. Clearly define Program Outcomes (POs) and Course Outcomes (COs).

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2. Align program curriculum, teaching–learning methodologies, and supporting facilities with the intended outcomes.
3. Develop systematic processes for assessment and evaluation to determine the extent of attainment.

Program Outcomes recognise what students are expected to know, demonstrate, and apply upon completion of the program. These outcomes should always be specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) to ensure clarity and effective evaluation.

The attainment of program outcomes depends not only on student performance in assessments but also on indirect factors such as perception, motivation, and engagement. Therefore, designing a proper attainment methodology—incorporating both direct assessment (tests, projects, practical’s) and indirect assessment (feedback, surveys)—is essential for ensuring the success of OBE implementation.

2. Methodology

Figure 1.1 Teaching Learning Process

This section describes in detail the methodology adopted for the attainment of the Course Outcomes (COs) in an engineering course within the Mechanical program. The overall Teaching–Learning Process cycle is illustrated in Figure 1.1, which demonstrates the systematic approach for defining, delivering, assessing, and improving outcomes.

2.1 Teaching–Learning Process

The process of attainment of COs and POs begins with the formulation of appropriate COs for each course in the three-year Diploma in Mechanical Engineering program.

1. Defining COs

- Course Outcomes are written by the respective course faculty using action verbs recommended by Bloom's Taxonomy [2].
- Each CO clearly specifies the knowledge or skill expected from students upon completion of the course.

2. CO–PO/PSO Correlation

- A correlation is established between COs and Program Outcomes (POs), as well as Program Specific Outcomes (PSOs).
- The mapping is done on a scale of:
 - 1 → Low correlation
 - 2 → Moderate correlation
 - 3 → Substantially high correlation
 - – → No relation

3. Delivery and Assessment

- The course contents are delivered as per a pre-prepared lesson plan aligned with COs.
- Assessment is carried out using a mix of tools such as internal tests, assignments, laboratory work, and semester-end examinations.

4. Evaluation and Continuous Improvement

- Based on student performance (marks obtained in assessments), attainment levels of each CO are calculated.
- Results are analysed by the course coordinator, and necessary actions are planned for continuous improvement (e.g., revising teaching strategies, conducting remedial classes).

2.2 Example: Course Outcomes (COs)

For the course *Tool Engineering (3361902)*, the following COs were defined:

- **3361902.1** Establish the importance of tool engineering in industry to enhance productivity and quality.
- **3361902.2** Select cutting tool and tool holder for the given application.
- **3361902.3** Select locating and clamping devices for the given component.
- **3361902.4** Select and design a jig and fixture for a simple component.
- **3361902.5** Select suitable press tool operation and calculate press tonnage and centre of pressure for a press tool component.
- **3361902.6** Select punch and die for a simple component.

2.3 Program Outcomes (POs) and Program Specific Outcomes (PSOs)

Program Outcomes correspond to the Graduate Attributes laid down by the NBA. These include fundamental knowledge, discipline knowledge, experiments and practices, use of tools, ethics, sustainability, teamwork, communication, and lifelong learning (PO1–PO10).

In addition, Program Specific Outcomes (PSOs) are defined for the Mechanical Engineering program:

- **PSO-1:** Apply program-specific principles to design, fabricate, operate, or demonstrate basic mechanical systems.

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- **PSO-2:** Plan and supervise manufacturing operations at the shop floor of machine tool-based manufacturing industries.

2.4 Sample CO–PO Mapping Matrix

Table 1 shows the mapping between COs and POs/PSOs for the course *Tool Engineering (3361902)*.

CO	PO1	PO2	PO3	PO4	PO5	PO6	PO7	PO8	PO9	PO10	PSO1	PSO2
3361902.1	–	3	2	2	–	–	2	2	2	2	–	2
3361902.2	–	3	2	2	2	–	2	1	2	2	2	2
3361902.3	–	3	2	2	–	–	2	–	2	2	2	2
3361902.4	–	3	3	3	3	–	2	2	2	3	2	2
3361902.5	–	3	–	3	–	–	2	2	2	2	2	2
3361902.6	–	3	3	3	–	–	2	–	2	2	2	2

2.5 Program-Level CO–PO Matrix

From the mapping matrices of COs and POs for all individual courses, a program-level CO–PO matrix is prepared by aggregating the data across all three years (including first-year courses). This consolidated matrix provides a holistic picture of Program Outcome attainment.

3. Attainment of Cos

Government Polytechnic Waghai, which is Gujarat Technological University (GTU) affiliated college. The Mechanical Engineering Department has decided to use Direct and Indirect assessment tools to measure attainment levels as below

Direct Assessment Tools	Indirect Assessment Tools
Mid-Semester Exam	Course Exit Survey
Assignments	Alumni survey
Quizzes	Employer survey
Performance during experiments	
Student activity	
End-of-Semester Exam	

The different weights are assigned to each above tools. As the university results are declared, the attainment level is calculated for regular students.

The NBA has given guidelines in the Self-Assessment Report (SAR) [3] has given guidelines for arriving at an attainment level

Attainment level 1: 75% of students score more than competence 40% target value

Attainment level 2: 85% of students score more than competence 40% target value

Attainment level 3: 95% of students score more than competence 40% target value

4. Sample calculations for the direct assessment method are as follows

S r N o	ENROLLMENT NO.	MID EXAM-1				MID EXAM-2				ASSIGNMENT						FINAL MARKS					
		C O 1	C O 2	C O 5	C O 6	C O 1	C O 2	C O 3	C O 4	C O 1	C O 3	C O 4	C O 5	C O 6	C O 1	C O 2	C O 3	C O 4	C O 5	C O 6	
		10	2	8	6	2	12	22	10	10	10	10	10	10	22	14	32	20	18	16	
1	156160319002	8	2	3	4	2	6	16	5	5	5	5	5	5	15	8	21	10	8	9	
2	156160319003	5	2	5	4	2	8	15	5	5	5	5	5	12	10	20	10	10	9		
6	156160319013	8	2	5	5	2	4	18	3	5	5	5	5	15	6	23	8	10	10		
7	156160319017	10	2	4	1	2	6	16	5	7	7	7	7	19	8	23	12	11	8		
10	156160319020	6	2	6	3	2	6	16	5	8	8	8	8	16	8	24	13	14	11		

SR. NO.	STUDENT ENROLLMENT NO							TOTAL	CO wise percentage					
		C O 1	C O 2	C O 3	C O 4	C O 5	C O 6		CO-1	C O- 2	C O- 3	CO-4	C O- 5	CO-6
		22	14	32	20	18	16	122						
1	156160319002	15	8	21	10	8	9	71	68.1	57.14	65.62	50	44.44	56.25
2	156160319003	12	10	20	10	10	9	71	54.54	71.42	62.5	50	55.55	56.25
3	156160319008	12	13	20	11	9	9	74	54.545	92.85	62.5	55	50	56.25
6	156160319013	15	6	23	8	10	10	72	68.18	42.85	71.87	40	55.55	62.5
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29	25	32	30	27	27
% of students scoring									87.8	75.7	96.9	90.9	81.8	81.8
									CO-1	Co-2	CO-3	CO-4	CO-5	CO-6
									2	1	3	2	1	1

The same procedure will be followed for MID TEST-2, ASSIGNMENT, Practical, and student activity as decided by a subject teacher.

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5. Sample calculation for the indirect assessment method

Government Polytechnic Waghai

Mechanical Engineering Department

Course Exit Survey

Tool Engineering (3361902)

Name of Faculty: Ketan Chaudhari

No of students 27

Sr No	Statements	Str on gly agr ee	Ag ree	Na tur al	Dis agr ee	Str on gly Di sa gr ee	
		5	4	3	2	1	
1	I can prepare a process and planning sheet used for the improvement of productivity.	13	8	2	4		
2	I can identify the tool signature.	13	8	2	4		
3	I can identify the locators and clamping devices used for jigs and fixtures	15	8	2	2		
4	I can apply the 3-2-1 location principle and design jigs and fixtures for a simple component	13	8	2	4		
5	I can calculate the working parameter for the press tool design	13	8	2	4		
6	I can calculate the dimensions of the die and punch	13	8	2	4		
7	Does the course content provide sufficient objective, knowledge and skill about the course?	13	8	2	4		
8	Classes are interactive, questions are encouraged, and doubts are effectively clarified.	13	8	2	4		
9	Teacher use presentation tools (blackboard, model, PPT, video) effectively?	13	8	2	4		
10	The test, assignment, tutorials and quizzes helped me to enhance my knowledge.	13	8	2	4		
11	Answer book shown to the students within the date?	13	8	2	4		
12	Solutions are displayed on the departmental notice board/ discussed in the classroom?	13	8	2	4		
13	Evaluation fair and transparent?	13	8	2	4		
14	I look upon the teacher as a capable counsellor concerning the academic, career and personal matters.	13	8	2	4		
Total		184	112	28	54	0	
Weightage							2.39

6. Final attainment of the course

CO WISE ATTAINMENT						
	MID EXAM ATTAINMENT	TERM WORK/ PRACTICAL ATTAINMENT	END SEM UNI. EXAM ATTAINMENT	UNIVERSITY PRACTICAL EXAM ATTAINMENT	WEIGHTED AVERAGE OF COs	CO Attainment
CO-1	2	2	2	2	2	2.08
CO-2	1	2	2	2	1.85	1.96
CO-3	3	2	2	2	2.15	2.2
CO-4	2	2	2	2	2	2.08
CO-5	1	2	2	2	1.85	1.96
CO-6	1	2	2	2	1.85	1.96

4. Results and Analysis

The attainment of Course Outcomes (COs) is decided by looking at student performance in mid-semester tests, assignments, and practical work. The average of these results gives the final attainment level of a CO.

4.1 Target Levels

In this study, the target level is set as *50% of students scoring above the decided benchmark*. Normally, this benchmark should be fixed by checking the last 3–4 years' university results for that course. It also depends on:

- Type of course (theory-heavy or practical).
- Quality of students admitted.
- Difficulty of the subject.

For example, in Diploma Mechanical Engineering, some subjects such as *Mathematics, Engineering Mechanics, Strength of Materials, and Theory of Machines* are tougher than others. Their results usually vary a lot, so the faculty member decides the target by looking at the past three years' results of that subject in the institute.

4.2 End-Semester Exam

In university end-semester exams, CO-wise marks are not available. So, the same attainment level is assumed for all COs of that course.

In this paper, the following weightages are used:

- End-Semester Exam (External):70%
- Internal Evaluation (Tests, Assignments, Practical's):30%

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4.3 Direct and Indirect Assessment

The final attainment of a CO is calculated using both direct and indirect assessments:

- Direct Assessment (80%) → Based on tests, assignments, semester exams, practical.
- Indirect Assessment (20%) → Based on surveys, student feedback, alumni inputs.

4.4 Final Attainment

The final attainment of a CO is found by combining direct and indirect methods. Then, by using the CO–PO mapping, the Program Outcome (PO) attainment is calculated.

Table 4 shows an example of CO–PO/PSO attainment values for the course *Tool Engineering*.

PO ATTAINMENT												
	PO-1	PO-2	PO-3	PO-4	PO-5	PO-6	PO-7	PO-8	PO-9	PO-10	PSO-1	PSO-2
3361902.1	-	2.08	1.39	1.39	-	-	1.39	1.39	1.39	1.39	-	1.39
3361902.2	-	1.96	1.31	1.31	1.31	-	1.31	1.31	1.31	1.31	1.31	1.31
3361902.3	-	2.2	1.47	1.47	-	-	1.47	2.2	1.47	1.47	1.47	1.47
3361902.4	-	2.08	2.08	2.08	2.08	-	1.39	2.08	1.39	2.08	1.39	1.39
3361902.5	-	1.96	-	1.96	-	-	1.31	-	1.31	1.31	1.31	1.31
3361902.6	-	1.96	1.96	1.96	-	-	1.31	1.31	1.31	1.31	1.31	1.31
33610902	-	2.04	1.64	1.7	1.7	-	1.36	1.66	1.36	1.48	1.36	1.36

5. Conclusion

The attainment of a course is calculated by looking at both direct and indirect assessments. Direct assessment includes tests, assignments, and exams, while indirect assessment includes surveys and feedback. Together, they give a complete picture of student learning.

In this paper, Course Outcomes (COs) are measured using two simple methods:

1. Rubrics for evaluating practical and assignment work.
2. Percentage of students scoring above a set target in internal tests and university exams, as suggested by the NBA.

After analysing the results, the attainment gap (difference between the target and actual performance) is identified. This gap is discussed by the course coordinator, module coordinator, and the program assessment committee. Based on this discussion, an action plan is made to improve weak areas.

This review process helps to find where students face difficulties and allows teachers to take steps to improve learning for the next batch of students. In this way, attainment analysis becomes a tool for continuous improvement in teaching and learning.

References

1. Spady, W.G. (1988). Organizing for results: the basis of authentic restructuring and reform, Educational Leadership, October, pp. 4-8.
2. A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing, Abridged Edition. Boston, MA: Allyn and Bacon. Anderson, L. W., & Krathwohl, D. R. (2001).
3. NBA guidelines in Self-Assessment Report (SAR)
4. <http://www.nbaind.org/files/evaluation-guidelinestier-ii-v0.pdf>
5. <http://www.nbaind.org/files/obe-and-nba%20accreditation.pdf>
6. Izham Zainal Abidinet. Al, (2009) Assessing the attainment of course outcomes for an engineering course, Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference of Teaching and Learning (ICTL 2009), Malaysia.
7. Surendar Rawat, Shruti Karkare, (2015) An Empirical study on Assessment of CO attainment for a Diploma Course, IJECET, vol 6, no.2, pp. 06- 12, 2015.
8. Geeta Deswal, Kumar Guarve, Ashwani Dhingra, Priyanka Kriplani, Bhawna Chopra and Rameshwar Dass, (2016) Assessment Method for Course Outcomes and Program Outcome, vol 2, no3, pp.58- 68, Academica Editores: ActaVelit, 2016.
9. PritiKudal, Vishakha Pawar, Deepika Thakare, Bhakti Nandurdikar, (2017) A Tool for Course Outcome Attainment, International Journal of Technical Research and Applications, vol 5, no 1, pp: 38-42, 2017.